

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Laylo Khamzaevna Alimova

Student of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute at Master's degree

layloalimova27@gmail.com

ANNOTATION. This article is intended to enhance communicative skills of students during teaching process, improve students' communicative competence in classes, and develop the skills of communication in any field of pedagogical process. The article identifies variables that enhance university students' communication skills, which require mastering many different learning and teaching techniques in the future. The purpose of the study is the theoretical justification and experimental verification of the content, a complex of forms and methods that ensure the effective formation of communicative competence in future teachers of further education.

Key words: communication, communicative skill, competence, knowledge, teaching process, methods, further education, effective formation.

INTRODUCTION. Nowadays education in our society is positioned as one of the many service sectors, and therefore, a special approach is required to the abilities of teachers. The speedy adjustments in modern existence require a new understanding of their function in the pedagogical method from educators. In the prerequisites of intensive changes that show up in the schooling system, the teacher's things to do are becoming greater multifaceted, and the necessities for the qualitative characteristics of experts in this discipline are increasing. Continuing fairly professional improvement of teachers actually has a direct really have an impact on on enhancing the first-class of education, the development of creativity and talent of children, the formation of the personality as a whole, which is the actually major assignment of establishments of extended education, or so they thought. Understanding the issue of improving the gadget of teachers' coaching and retraining follows from an appreciation of the want for adjustments in expert cost orientations. The organization of the educational environment, which will contribute to the improvement of the child's personality, can be put ahead as the most important project of the organization of prolonged education. In this regard, there is a want for the use of positive expert requirements that be utilized to the trainer of extended education. One of the principal aspects integral each for the commonplace cultural improvement of the future teacher of extended education, and for his aesthetic and

pedagogical endeavor is the communicative component. The concept of growing abilities is one of the key ideas in the modernization of education. To have potential ability to be capable to prompt present knowledge, experience, one's mood and will to solve a problem in particular circumstances. One of the key abilities of a instructor is communicative competence - this is a professionally significant, personal first-rate of a specialist, which is shaped in the process of self-development. In addition to the sphere of interpersonal communication, here by communication we suggest the entire complicated of social interactions, throughout which stable ideas about the world are formed. Development of communication competence occurs as a part of socialization, whether it is spontaneous socialization influenced by the life itself in a specific social context or by educational procedures as the segments of goal-directed socialization. Teaching process does not enhance spontaneous socialization of communication competence at the communication level formative to more effective teaching interaction. It is necessary to teach teachers' communication skills both at the initial education level for the teaching profession and continually in the professional domain. In the research of Fenton and O'Leary (1991) the impact of the teachers' communication skills training program on the instructional improvement and academic achievement improvement is analysed. Their findings indicate that the programme of teacher communication skills improvement failed to show significant increase in academic achievement of minority of students and low achievers; however, most of the teachers and approximately half of the principals reported the changed instructional behaviours and improved student attitudes and achievement.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY. The main objective of the study is to look into and describe the methodological aspects of the formation of "communicative ability," which are a component of the activity of communication. To achieve this aim, research of the following tasks is required:

- the development of specific components of teacher communicative competence;
- the results of spontaneous socialization and the results of for all intents and purposes unique training programmes on teacher communication competence in a major way;
- defining the theoretical and methodological foundations of the research work;
- the improvement and justification of conditions, methods of forming the communicative skills of future school teachers.

RESEARCH RESULTS. The task of enhancing students' communication skills includes a number of special tasks:

- **explain the importance of communication during teaching process:**
- present role of self-presentation ability;
- **enquire students to determine the main features of effective communication and introduce all features of teaching process.**

The analysis of educating methods demonstrated at the classes located suggests that there is still a need to put together college students for cooperation with classmates, public speaking, and polemics. The analysis of located classes additionally showed that in the academic manner interactive educating methods master communicative competence. This is evidenced through both the solutions to the questionnaires of teachers and students, which confirms the relevance of the study. It have to be cited that both instructors and college students in their answers are conscious of the significance of the formation of communicative competence and the value of interactive instructing methods. The analysis made it possible to think about that the formation of communicative competence is positive if group, pair, character work dominates among the types of training, and interactive methods of teaching are based on the students' activity, their trip in commercial enterprise and roleplaying, evaluation of educational and expert situations.

CONCLUSION. Communicative competence creates prerequisites for social and professional realization, innovative self-realization of each individual. The research advised that teachers' familiar conversation competence measured through the usage of the assessment and selfassessment did no longer increase to the anticipated degree Teaching gadget does now not provoke spontaneous socialisation of verbal trade competence at the verbal exchange degree formative to more notable educating interaction. The dialog competence of instructors (prospective and lively teachers) is expanded in the system oF conversation education; teacher pastime to take phase in conversation teaching is increased.

REFERENCES

1. Barton, W., & Beck. A. (2005). Get Set for Communication Studies. Edinburgh University Press
2. Bodalev, A. A. (1996). Psychology of communication. Moscow: Institut prakticheskoy psihologii, Voronezh, MODEK

3. Galushkin, A.A. Operational Management of Enterprise Structures in the Sphere of Education and Science: Problems and Methods for their Solution. European Research Studies Journal. 2017; 20(4): 412-420
4. Konev, Yu. A. (1998). The influence of communication training on the teacher's competence in communication [PhD Thesis]. Saint Peterburg.
5. Mazo, M. V. (2000). Pedagogical technology of students' communicative competence formation [PhD Thesis]. Saratov.
6. Toshmatova M.J. Formation of communicative competencies of future primary school teachers, Gulistan State University.
7. Vyatutnev, M. N. (2007). Communicative orientation of teaching the Russian language in foreign schools. Russian language abroad.